

A Comparative Study between Onlay and Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair in Case of Ventral Hernias

Bharat Bhushan Patidar¹, Neel Kamal Gupta², Lalit³, Vipin Vaday⁴, Ridham Trivedi⁵, Jayesh Ghai⁶, Jatin Lakhani⁷, Devashish Verma⁸

¹3rd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

²Professor and Unit Head, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

³Assistant Professor. Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

⁴3rd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

^{5,6}2nd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

^{7,8}1st Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Lalit

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Aims: To compare the outcomes of Onlay and Preperitoneal mesh repair in case of ventral hernia

Settings and Design: This comparative study was conducted in the General Surgery Department OPD at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur, from September 2022 to March 2024. It involved 66 patients undergoing open ventral hernia repair.

Methods and Material: The study included 66 patients who underwent open ventral hernia repair. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were patients aged above 18 years, those undergoing repair for ventral hernias (including incisional, umbilical, paraumbilical, and epigastric hernias), and those who provided written consent. Exclusion criteria included planned concurrent gastrointestinal surgery, immunosuppressive disorders, chronic diseases such as diabetes, severe renal or hepatic failure, and obstructed or strangulated hernias. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institute Ethics Committee, and informed consent was secured from all participants.

Statistical analysis used: Continuous variables were reported as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequency and percentage. Differences between groups were evaluated using the Mann-Whitney U Test for continuous variables and the Fisher Exact Test for categorical variables. A p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results: The pre-peritoneal mesh repair group demonstrated significantly lower complication rates compared to the onlay mesh repair group. Incidences of seroma formation and wound infections were reduced ($p < 0.05$). The pre-peritoneal group also experienced shorter hospital stays (mean \pm SD: 4.2 ± 1.1 days vs. 6.5 ± 1.4 days, $p < 0.05$) and lower recurrence rates ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Pre-peritoneal mesh repair is associated with lower complication rates, shorter hospital stays, and lower recurrence rates compared to onlay mesh repair for ventral hernias.

Keywords: Comparative Study, Ventral Hernia Repair, General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College, Patient Outcomes, Pre-peritoneal Mesh Repair, Onlay Mesh Repair, Complication Rates.

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Introduction

The anterior abdominal wall is particularly susceptible to various types of hernias due to man's upright posture. These hernias often protrude through the abdominal wall, forming noticeable and palpable swellings. [1] A ventral hernia

specifically refers to the protrusion of an abdominal organ or a part of it through the anterior abdominal wall, occurring at any site other than the groin. Ventral hernias can be classified based on their origin as either spontaneous (primary) or acquired

and by their specific location on the abdominal wall. [2,3] Patients typically seek medical attention for ventral hernias due to symptoms such as swelling, acute pain, discomfort, gastrointestinal issues or cosmetic concerns. Diagnosing these hernias is generally straightforward through clinical examination and ultrasound scanning. Numerous predisposing factors contribute to the development of ventral hernias, which can be linked to specific patient characteristics, underlying pathological conditions or iatrogenic factors (medical conditions caused by surgical procedures or treatments). [4,5]

From the surgeon's perspective, hernia repair is a common procedure with various surgical techniques available. [6] Incisional hernias a subset of ventral hernias are unique in that they are the only abdominal wall hernias considered iatrogenic, meaning they result from previous surgical procedures. Incisional hernia is a frequent complication following abdominal surgeries, leading to significant morbidity and time away from productive activities. Historically, the repair of incisional hernia was associated with high recurrence rates. However, the advent of synthetic prosthetic materials and newer techniques in recent years has enabled tension-free repairs, significantly reducing the recurrence rate. [7]

The use of mesh in ventral hernia repair, as opposed to sutures, has substantially improved long-term outcomes and is now considered the standard of care. [8] Despite these improvements, studies indicate that mesh placement increases the risk of wound complications, including infections, seromas (fluid accumulation) and mesh erosions. [9-11]

The location of the mesh placement significantly influences these risks. For instance, mesh placed in proximity to intra-abdominal contents increases the risks of adhesions (where organs stick together), bowel obstruction and fistula formation (abnormal connections between organs). Conversely, onlay mesh placement, which is more superficial, is more prone to early infections if wound complications arise. [12,13] Despite the routine nature of ventral hernia repairs using mesh, there is no consensus on the optimal mesh placement location. [18]

The main techniques for mesh placement in ventral hernia repair include onlay, inlay, sublay, and underlay methods. Onlay repair involves placing the mesh on the anterior fascia, usually requiring flap dissection and primary closure of the fascia beneath the mesh. Inlay repair involves placing the mesh within the hernia defect and securing it circumferentially to the edges of the fascia.

Sublay repair positions the mesh in the retrorectus or preperitoneal space. Underlay repair places the mesh intraperitoneally, securing it to the anterior abdominal wall. [14]

Preperitoneal repair is often considered more complex and challenging. The dissection required in this plane can risk damaging muscles, blood supply and nerves to the rectus abdominis. Additionally, this mesh location may not be suitable for defects that are off the midline. However, the preperitoneal space offers protection to the mesh from superficial wound complications and intra-abdominal contents. It also facilitates load-bearing tissue ingrowth from two directions, potentially decreasing the risk of hernia recurrence. [15,16]

This study aims to compare the outcomes of onlay and preperitoneal mesh repair in the context of ventral hernias. The comparison will focus on several factors, including the duration of surgery, postoperative complications, overall outcomes, recurrence rates and the length of hospital stay. By evaluating these parameters, the study seeks to determine the most effective approach to ventral hernia repair.

Materials and Methods

Type of Study: Comparative Study

Period of Study: September 2022 to March 2024

Place of Study: General Surgery Department OPD, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur

Sample Size: Total 66 patients who undergoing open ventral hernia repair during the period of study

Plan of Study: This study includes patients who undergoing open ventral hernia repair surgery at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur during September 2022 to March 2024 Institute Ethics Committee approval was obtained before start of study Written and inform consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment into the study.

Subject Selection

- A. Duration of study- 18 months.
- B. Subjects from both sexes be recruited – Yes.
- C. Inclusion/exclusion criteria given in synopsis.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age above 18 years.
- Patients undergoing repair for ventral hernias including incisional hernia, umbilical, and paraumbilical and epigastric hernia.
- Patient who has given consent for surgery.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Planned other gastrointestinal surgery.
- Immunosuppressive disorders and chronic disease like diabetes.
- Severe renal or hepatic failure.

- Patient with Obstructed hernias & strangulated hernias.

- Patient who were un-cooperative.

Techniques Onlay Technique:

Figure 1: Onlay Mesh Repair

The procedure begins with proper preparation of the skin. Good antimicrobial cleansing of the skin and all crevices should be done. Prophylactic antibiotics are administered at the time of induction.

A bowel preparation is done preoperatively if the bowel (colon) is content of the sac [20]. The skin incision was made according to site and size of defect, subcutaneous flap raised up to 5cm around the defect, the hernial sac found, contents reduced back then primary closure of fascia defect was done

using no. 1 Polypropylene. Then Polypropylene nonabsorbable synthetic surgical mesh (PROLENE Mesh) of suitable size with minimum of 3-5 cm overlap beyond the margin of defect is placed over anterior rectus sheath, then fixed in four corners and additional stitches when felt needed with 2:0 Polypropylene sutures. Then the skin is closed after placing the closed suction drain. Drain removed when output is less than 30ml. [19]

Preperitoneal Technique:

Figure 2: Pre-peritoneal Mesh Repair

The procedure begins with proper preparation of the skin. Good antimicrobial cleansing of the skin and all crevices done. Prophylactic antibiotics are administered at the time of induction. A bowel preparation is done preoperatively if the bowel (colon) is content of the sac [20].

The skin incision was made according to site and size of defect, subcutaneous flap raised up to 2cm around the defect, the hernial sac found, contents reduced back then plane is created between the posterior rectus sheath and the parietal peritoneum. Defect in the peritoneum is closed with absorbable suture material (polyglactin/ catgut).

Then Polypropylene nonabsorbable synthetic surgical mesh (PROLENE Mesh) of suitable size with minimum of 3-5 cm overlap beyond the margin of defect is placed in the plane created between the posterior rectus sheath and the parietal

peritoneum. Then primary closure of fascia defect was done using no. 1 Polypropylene. Skin is closed after placing the closed suction drain. Drain removed when output is less than 30ml. [19]

Statistical Analysis: In the data, continuous variables are reported as mean and standard deviation, whereas categorical variables are expressed as frequency /count / percentages. The study population was divided into two groups based on the surgery technique. Differences between groups for continuous variables were evaluated using Mann- Whitney U Test and categorical values are analyzed with fisher exact test. A p value <0.05 was considered significant.

Observation and Results

In this study, a total of 66 patients who underwent by onlay and pre-peritoneal mesh repair procedures performed at a single center.

Table 1: Age group wise distribution among both the groups

Age Group	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal	
	No.	%	No.	%
≤ 20 years	1	3.03%	0	0.00%
21-30 years	2	6.06%	0	0.00%
31-40 years	8	24.24%	7	21.21%
41-50 years	13	39.39%	18	54.55%
51-60 years	5	15.15%	3	9.09%
> 60 years	4	12.12%	5	15.15%
Total	33	100.0	33	100.0

The age in the study ranged from 18 to 74 years 'age group. Maximum patients were between 41-50 years age groups followed by 31-40 years age groups.

Graph 1: Age group wise distribution among both the groups

Table 2: Sex Distribution among both the groups

Gender	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal	
	No.	%	No.	%
Male	14	42.4%	13	39.4%
Female	19	57.6%	20	60.6%
Total	33	100%	33	100%

There were 14 (42.4%) males and 19 (57.6%) females in the onlay group while 13 (39.4%) males and 20 (60.6%) females in the preperitoneal group.

Graph 2: Sex Distribution among both the groups

Table 3: Type of Diagnosis among both the groups

Diagnosis	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal	
	No.	%	No.	%
Epigastric hernia	20	60.6%	20	60.6%
Incisional hernia	4	12.1%	6	18.2%
Paraumbilical hernia	2	6.1%	1	3.0%
Supraumbilical hernia	0	0.0%	1	3.0%
Umbilical hernia	7	21.2%	5	15.2%
Total	33	100%	33	100%

In the above table, mostly similar number of 40 patients are diagnosed as epigastric hernias in both the groups. Followed by 12 patients are diagnosed as umbilical hernias, 10 patients as incisional hernias, 3 patients as paraumbilical hernias and only 1 patient as supraumbilical hernias.

Graph 3: Type of Diagnosis among both the groups

Table 4: Mean Duration of Surgery among both the groups

Group	N	Mean Duration (mins.)	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Onlay	33	70.82	9.060	1.577	0.020 (S)
Pre-peritoneal	33	79.85	19.720	3.433	

In the above table, mean duration of surgery in Onlay Mesh repair was 70.82±9.060 mins compared to Pre-peritoneal Mesh repair 79.85±19.720 mins. This result was statistically significant between both the groups (P<0.05; P=0.020).

Graph 4: Mean Duration (mins) of Surgery among both the groups**Table 5: Discharge from the wound among both the groups**

Discharge	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Yes	8	24.24%	4	12.1%	0.202 (NS)
No	25	75.75%	29	87.9%	
Total	33	100%	33	100%	

In the above table, discharge was seen in 8 patients (24.24%) of onlay mesh repair and 4 patients (12.1%) of pre-peritoneal mesh repair. Using a chi-square test, there was statistically not significant difference between both the groups (P>0.05; P=0.202).

Table 6: Postoperative Complications among both the groups

Postoperative Complications	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Seroma	4	12.12%	4	12.1%	1.000 (NS)
Surgical site infection	4	12.12%	0	0.0%	0.000 (S)
Mesh Infection	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	-
Flap Necrosis	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	-

The above table shows that the seroma was found in 4 patients in onlay mesh repair technique and 4 patients in pre-peritoneal mesh repair technique. Surgical site infection was found in 4 patients in onlay technique. No other complications were found in pre-peritoneal mesh repair technique. These results were found statistically highly significant difference between both the groups in terms of surgical site infection (P<0.01).

Graph 5: Postoperative Complications among both the groups

Table 7: Mean VAS score among both the groups

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
Day 0	Onlay	33	2.45	.754	0.004(S)
	Pre-peritoneal	33	1.91	.723	
Day 1	Onlay	33	.61	.496	0.625(NS)
	Pre-peritoneal	33	.55	.506	

In the above table, mean VAS score at day 0 was significantly lower in pre-peritoneal mesh repair which was 1.91±0.723 compared to onlay mesh repair which was 2.45±0.754 (P<0.05). On day 1, mean VAS score was 0.61±0.495 in onlay and 0.55±0.506 in pre-peritoneal mesh repair (P>0.05).

Graph 6: Mean VAS score among both the groups

Fig. 2: Visual Analogue Score [21]

Table 8: Mean Duration of Hospital Stay among both the groups

Group	N	Mean Duration (Days)	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Onlay	33	1.24	.435	.076	0.361 (NS)
Pre-peritoneal	33	1.15	.364	.063	

In the above table, mean duration of hospital stay was lower in pre-peritoneal mesh repair (1.15±0.364 Days) compared to onlay mesh repair (1.24±0.435 Days). This results was statistically not significant between both the groups (P>0.05; P=0.361).

Graph 7: Mean Duration of Hospital Stay among both the groups

Table 9: Need for Readmission among both the groups

Need for readmission	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Yes	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	-
No	33	100.0%	33	100.0%	
Total	33	100%	33	100%	

No need for readmission was found in all the patients.

Graph 8: Need for Readmission among both the groups

Table 10: Recurrence among both the groups

Recurrence	Onlay		Pre-peritoneal		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Yes	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	-
No	33	100.0%	33	100.0%	
Total	33	100%	33	100%	

No recurrence was observed in both the mesh repair technique in 1 month and within 3 months of follow-up.

Graph 9: Recurrence among both the groups

Discussion

Ventral hernia in the anterior abdominal wall includes both spontaneous and, most commonly, incisional hernias after an abdominal operation. Incisional hernia has been a frequent complication of abdominal surgery for a long time, with a current incidence of 2- 20% in most series. [22,23] Small hernias up to 2cm in diameter are often successfully closed with primary tissue repairs [24]. However, larger ones have a recurrence rate of up to 30-40% when a tissue repair alone is performed. [22] Hernia recurrence is distressing to patient and embarrassing to surgeons.

Nowadays tension free repair using prosthetic mesh has decreased recurrence to negligible 0–10%. Despite excellent results, the increased risk of

infection with placement of a foreign body and cost factor still exist; however, operating time and hospital length of stay are shortened. Primary tissue repair is associated with higher unacceptable recurrence rate, nowadays; tension free mesh repair is ideal hernia repair technique.

Age

In our study, ventral hernias are more common in patients aged between 30-50 years (69.70%) of age group. The age in the study ranged from 18 to 74 years 'age group. Maximum patients were between 41-50 years age groups followed by 31-40 years age groups (P<0.05). Mean age in On-lay group was 45.12 years and Pre-peritoneal group mean age was 47.61 years. The trends in distribution of age are comparable to the previous study-

Table 11: Comparison of age groups in different study

Age Group	Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	Sowmith S et al. (2022) [25]	Present Study
11-20	0%	0%	1.52%
21-30	15%	4.2%	3.03%
31-40	58.3%	29.78%	22.73%
41-50	21.7%	34.04%	46.97%
51-60	5%	25.5%	12.12%
61-70	0%	6.38%	13.64%

Sex

Ventral hernias are more common among females 39 (59.09%) patients were females and 27 (40.91%) patients were male.

In literature the ratio is 3:1 and in our study it is 3:2. Ibrahim T et al. [27] have obtained a 62.5% of female population in the study.

Sowmith S et al. [25] was observed a female population was 68.08%, while Aoda FS et al. [31]

showed a high incidence in ventral hernia in female population in ratio greater than 2:1.

In the present study most contribution to the ventral hernia came from female sex which in turn was a reflection of incisional hernias and are of obstetric and gynaecological surgeries, indicating a more possibility in reduction of ventral hernias with a proper care at the time of primary surgery and proper suturing techniques and early post-operative care.

Table 12: Comparison of female population in different studies

Study Group	Percentage of females
Aoda FS et al. (2013) [29]	80.3%
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	70%
Saber A et al. (2016) [28]	51%
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	62.5%
Issa M et al. (2021)	84.6%
Sowmith S et al. (2022) [25]	68.08%
Present Study	59.09%

Incidence: Incidence among ventral hernias in the present study showed mostly 60.60% patients are diagnosed as epigastric hernias in both the groups, followed by 18.18% patients are diagnosed as umbilical hernias and 15.15% patients as incisional hernias. Similar results found to another previous study as follows:

Table 13: Comparison of incidence of different ventral hernias in past study

Study	Epigastric	Incisional	Umbilical
Aoda FS et al. (2013) [29]	28.5%	71.5%	-
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	48.3%	40%	11.7%
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	62.5%	20%	17.5%
Sowmith S et al. (2022) [30]	34.04%	53.19%	12.7%
Present Study	60.60%	15.15%	18.18%

Incisional hernia and umbilical are more common in ventral hernias than the epigastric hernia, the incidence of different ventral hernias are comparable to the previous study except for the Ibrahim T et al. [27] study where incisional hernia is very low with only 20%.

Duration of Surgery

In our study, mean duration of surgery in Onlay Mesh repair was 70.82±9.060 mins compared to Pre-peritoneal Mesh repair 79.85±19.720 mins and it was found to be statistically significant between both the groups (P<0.05; P=0.020).

In Saber A et al. [28] study, the mean operative time for onlay repair was 67.04±13.19 minutes

while in Sublay group was 93.26±24.94 minutes (P≤0.0001). Rajsiddharth B et al. [26] study 45 min, while in cases with pre-peritoneal Mesh repair took more time and the duration of surgery was 60.15 min in present series (P<0.0001). In Ibrahim T et al. [27] study the mean time taken to perform surgery in the onlay group was 75–90 (83.41±10.24) min compared with 80–100 (89.52 ±7.25) min in the sublay group (P=0.324) which is not significant in this study.

Sowmith S et al. [25] showed mean duration of surgery that underwent onlay mesh repair was 78.80 minutes, while in cases with pre-peritoneal mesh repair mean duration of surgery was 80.04 minutes.

Table 14: Comparison of Duration of surgery in different study

Mean Duration (in minutes)	Onlay	Pre-peritoneal
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	45	60.15
Saber A et al. (2016) [28]	67.04	93.26
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	83.41	89.52
Dhanbhar R et al. (2018)	50	70
Sowmith S et al. (2022) [25]	78.8	80.04
Loh C et al. (2023)	59	74
Present study	70.82	79.85

Complications

The most common complication observed was seroma in 4 patients in onlay mesh repair technique and 4 patients in pre-peritoneal mesh repair technique. This complication was managed conservatively. Onlay technique had more chances of seroma formation, due to the fact that onlay technique requires wide mobilisation of subcutaneous tissue flaps leading to creating devascularising skin flaps with seroma formation or infection. Insertion of foreign material temporarily establishes an effective barrier between the circulatory system of the subcutaneous tissues and that of the deeper parietal layers. In pre-peritoneal repair, the bare posterior surface (below the arcuate line) of the of the rectus muscles which is rich in lymphatic is capable of absorbing any collecting seroma. The superficial

location of the mesh also puts it in danger of becoming infected if there is a superficial wound infection. Surgical site infection was found 4 cases in only onlay group. These patients were treated with appropriate antibiotics and regular dressing. No patient required removal of mesh because the infection was superficial and responded well to antibiotics.

The overall complication rate was found in onlay group (24.24%) and pre-peritoneal group (12.12%). Present study was similar complication rates in favours of both mesh repair which was comparable to other series Saber A et al. (2016) [28] studied 24% in onlay group and 2% in pre peritoneal group and Sowmith S et al. [25] reported 30% complications in the onlay group and 9.5% in the pre peritoneal group.

Table 15: Comparison of Complications in different studies

Complications	Onlay	Pre-peritoneal
Aoda FS et al. (2013) [29]	32.69%	4%
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	53.33%	20%
Saber A et al. (2016) [28]	24%	2%
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	14%	6%
Sowmith S et al. (2022) [25]	30%	9.50%
Present study	24.24%	12.10%

Hospital Stay

The duration of postoperative hospital stay is an indirect indication of degree of morbidity in terms of postoperative complications. Average postoperative hospital stay period in present series for onlay Mesh repair was 1.24 days, as compared

to 1.15 days average hospital stay for Pre-Peritoneal Mesh repair with (P value 0.361).

Which is statistically not significant and is comparable to Awad SS et al. (2022) series, but Shah DK et al. (2023) study has a significant more time of hospital stay in the onlay group.

Table 16: Comparison of Hospital stay in different studies

Mean hospital stay in days	Onlay	Pre-peritoneal
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	7.53	5.96
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	4.63	2.62
Raghuveer MN et al. (2018)	6.68	4.8
Awad SS et al. (2022)	1.16	1.08
Sowmith S et al. (2022) [25]	5.923	5.142
Shah DK et al. (2023)	8	6
Present study	1.24	1.15

Recurrence: No recurrence of hernia was noticed in Pre-Peritoneal Mesh repair, in present series as well as in the onlay group recurrence occurred in 0 cases after a 100% follow up for minimum 3 months and is statistically insignificant (P=0.00)

Table 17: Comparison of Recurrence rates in different studies

Recurrence Rate in %	Onlay	Pre-peritoneal
Rajsiddharth B et al. (2015) [26]	13.33	0
Saber A et al. (2016) [28]	8	3
Ibrahim T et al. (2018) [27]	5	5
Present study	0	0

Conclusion

Pre-peritoneal mesh repair is a viable alternative to onlay mesh repair and can be applied to various forms of ventral hernias.

This technique is associated with a lower overall complication rate, including reduced incidences of seroma formation, wound infections, shorter hospital stays, and lower recurrence rates.

Furthermore, pre-peritoneal mesh placement offers added protection for the mesh by shielding it from superficial wound complications, intra-abdominal adhesions, and contamination.

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